

MODERN GAME-BASED APPROACH TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article analyzes highly effective methods for learning English by using contemporary games such as Duolingo and Kahoot. Duolingo allows learners to study English more effectively and productively through its scoring. Students use it anytime and anywhere, it provides being flexible. Kahoot is a powerful learning tool that makes lessons more enjoyable. Its game-based format increases student motivation and encourages active participation. It makes learning interactive, competitive and effective and also the platform provides instant feedback, helping teachers quickly assess students' understanding. The study discusses the use of digital games, role-playing activities, and educational games in English language classrooms.

Keywords: modern methods, problem-solving, Duolingo, Kahoot, quizzes, points, scores, rate, interactive.

Introduction. In today's world, learning English is not just about tutorials, books, or grammar rules. Modern methods use games and interactive lessons to make learning interesting and productive. Students can learn new vocabulary, grammar, listening and speaking skills through games, and this process engages them. Learners get motivated by points, scores, and problem-solving activities which also provide opportunities to practise English in real time situations.

One of the most popular games is Duolingo. It allows learners to study English effectively and easily through its scoring and level system. Duolingo is really effective and useful and many users have reported benefits from using it. One of its main advantages is that it is free and convenient. The lessons are step-by-step, starting from basic words and gradually becoming more challenging, which makes learning easy to follow. The lessons are short, usually 5-10 minutes, making it easy to practice daily. However, Duolingo alone is not enough for developing full speaking or real-life conversation. For the best results, it is recommended to combine Duolingo with speaking practice, reading, writing, and listening to English media. According to research published in the journal *Languages Learning and Technology* Smith, Jiang

and Peters ,2024,Duolingo significantly improves learner's reading and listening skills after regular use for three months.Moreover,Duolingo is a well-developed language learning app.Every lesson is interactive and encourages students to be active .It immediately checks and shows mistakes ,allowing students to correct them.Learners can use it anytime,and anywhere ,which makes studying English very convenient and flexible .Furthermore,there is another research .According to Sibuea ,Purba,and Mulya 2025 ,students who used Duolingo improved their English vocabulary skills significantly ,which shows that the application is effective for language learning.

Another popular game for learning English is Kahoot .Kahoot is an online quiz and learning platform.It provides interactive lessons through quizzes ,where students answer questions gain points , and see their ranking on the leaderboard .It is widely used in classrooms,training sessions,and group activities.This game increases student's motivation and engagement because the points and competition encourage them to participate actively.The game works in a question-and -answer format with multiple choice options .Teachers and trainers can also add images ,videos,and different types of questions to make the quizzes more interesting. It makes learning English more enjoyable and effective ,especially for vocabulary and grammar practice.According to a study published in Acuity :Journal of English Language Pedagogy ,using Kahoot,significantly improved vocabulary retention and motivation among sixth-grade students.Another important advantage of Kahoot is that it encourages active participacation from all students .In a normal classroom,some students may be shy or afraid to speak in front of others.With Kahoot ,every student can answer questions using their phone,tablet , or computer.This allows even quiet or less confident students to take part in the lesson without fear .Teachers can involve the whole class at the same time,ensuring that no student is left behind.Kahoot also helps to develop quick thinking and decision-making skills.Each question in Kahoot is usually limeted by time,which means students must think fast and choose the correct answer quickly.This improves their consentration ,reaction speed, and ability to make decisions under pressure .These skills are not only useful in education but also very important in real-life situations.

According to Dave Dodgson:"Introducing English-language learners to game-based learning brings the added benefits of conversation about their interests, discussion of in-class rules, and peer collaboration.

Game-based learning (GBL) is an area of education that has been getting a lot of attention in recent times. It's easy to find articles and entire websites devoted to the

power of games for engaging learners and providing a vehicle for their learning. However, many of these articles seem to focus on math, science, and language arts.

But what about language learning? How can GBL help English-language learners develop their comprehension and communicative skills? Well, the short answer is very similar to the above: it can engage ELLs and give them an inspiration and a context for communicating. I've spent many years working with language learners in different countries, and they are always eager to talk about their personal interests, especially when it comes to video games.

The one question that I'm often asked, however, is: "How can teachers get started with GBL in the language classroom, especially when they have little experience of it?" The remainder of this post is my response.

Start a Conversation

GBL is all about engaging learners, so your first step is to find out if they like the idea -- after all, there's little point in trying to push GBL with a class who are simply not into gaming! (Such classes are rare, but they do exist.)

Ask your students what kind of games interest them and what their devices of choice are. Learn about their gaming habits, and find out how they balance game time with their other out-of-school activities. Exchange opinions on how much gaming is too much. Show an interest, and use this information to help you bring games into class.

And make sure that you have a conversation with your colleagues as well. Anyone else interested in GBL will most likely be delighted to help with advice and ideas. Let's not forget the other stakeholders, too. Keep your school administration and the parents in the loop about your GBL plans to avoid any misunderstandings (like the difference between "playing" and "learning") further down the line.

The Power of Choice

Once you've started the conversation with your ELLs, it's important that you keep it going. Involve them in the choice of what games or apps to use in class. This will make them even more invested in the process. Here are two ways that I've done this:

The game should not be inappropriate in any way for learners of their age.

It should be either free or cheap.

It must work on the devices available to the class (school-owned equipment or BYOD).

Set the Rules

It is always a dangerous assumption with GBL (or any other use of edtech, for that matter) to expect the students to be automatically wowed into staying on task and taking the work seriously. Classroom management is as important as ever in these situations, and I find that having clear rules helps.

First and foremost is a reminder that we are still in class, and we are here to learn. If anyone just wants to play, they can do so at home. There will be set tasks just like any other lesson, and all normal school rules and expectations still apply".

Game based learning is important not only for learning English but also in other fields. I am going to give some examples. According to Heather Sanderell, "When I taught kindergarten, I needed to more explicit instruction of device usage and game navigation because my students had less experience with games and technology. I had access to iPads, which are more user-friendly for little learners. Often, there is no login required, which is good for young students who are still learning how to identify their letters and may not be ready to type. Kindergarten students were very excited to use iPads and had some familiarity with touch screens, which was helpful. I would show my students the picture of the app so they knew what to click. If time permitted, I would hand out the devices with the apps opened already. As with older students, it is important to provide direct instruction and modeling on how to play the games, as well as expectations for using technology in the classroom. Quizziz was a favourite game for my kindergarten students on the iPads. I created games for my students to practice their rhyming skills and CVC (consonant-vowel-consonant) (Use this CVC words game to help your class better understand what CVC words are, while also having some fun

and staying engaged at the same time. Matching activities like this one are perfect for revising tough topics. Using interactive puzzle elements as the gameplay for the activity means that it tests your children's problem-solving skills as well as their knowledge of the subject. This makes the learning process far more effective, and also aids cognitive development as a result. What are CVC words? A CVC word is a single syllable, three-letter word that is structured consonant-vowel-consonant. There is an abundance of words in the English language that fall in this category, as it is a very common structure for shorter words. Learning about CVC words is an important tool in phonics as it can help children with reading, writing, and rhyming three-letter words. Some examples of words with the CVC structure are: cat, dog, rat, cut) word decoding .I used lots of clip-art images when creating - games as they have limited reading skills".

An edtech teaching toolkit should include reliable tools for your needs and circumstances .Whether that includes Kahoot !, Screencast-O-Matic , or Scratch, it's ultimately about your teacher- student relationship . Kahoot! According to Vicki Davis "My students beg to play Kahoot! But ,to me ,the power is seeing how many students know the answers and reteaching on the spot. Tips:1 .Play each Kahoot ! set more than once, randomizing the order of questions and answers. This helps students practice and learn. 2. Let students create and share their own games. 3. Embed videos and graphics relating to the topic to improve retention .Furthermore, creating and answering questions from different parts of a literary work using Kahoot helps students understand the book as a whole. Preparing questions for each section encourages students to read more carefully and stay focused. It also helps them understand the main events, key ideas, and important situations in the text. As a result, students develop deeper comprehension rather than just memorizing information. Students analyze the characters' personalities, situations, the author's ideas, and the main meaning of the book through the process of answering questions. Not only that, but it also develops their comprehension and critical thinking skills. Although it is an interactive activity, it still strengthens deep understanding and meaningful learning.

In conclusion, a modern approach to learn English through games brings new methods into the classroom .It allows learners to use English in different situations and activities. Game-based learning supports language practice in a natural way. For this reason, modern game-based approaches are valuable in English language education.

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